

Towards understanding customer co-creation experience for mass customization

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Abstract. Mass-Customization (MC) has been considered to answer diversifying customer needs and reshape the consumer product market. However, after about two decades of trials, MC has been largely far from success in practice. One of the major reasons for this is considered to be lack of user engagement with customized products and the customization process itself. Therefore, this draws the attention from what is provided to the customer to how it is provided. The user involvement in MC is in the form of co-creation and often done through online tools, also known as product configurators. In practice, these product configurators for MC fail frequently in sales conversion. This study investigates the experience for customers throughout the co-creation process in an attempt to shed a light on different aspects of this experience and provide a better understanding of all contributing factors.

Keywords: Mass-Customization · Co-creation · Product configurators · User Experience

1 Introduction

Customer needs are individualizing and in order to cater these increasingly diversifying wants and needs, many businesses have been widely implementing the strategy of Mass-Customization (MC). MC provides customers goods and services that meet their individual needs, while maintaining a near mass production efficiency (Tseng & Jiao 2001). This means that within MC, customers are integrated into the creation of value by defining, configuring, designing, matching, or modifying their individual solution out of a list of options and pre-defined components, whilst businesses are still able to maintain a mass production system (Piller, 2004). Due to the rapid development of information and manufacturing technologies, businesses have been able to offer increasingly more and intricate ways of customization and personalization to satisfy customer needs. While MC enables the customer to add value by choosing from a predetermined set of options, Mass-Personalization (MP)

enables a business to identify and apply exact customer preferences by obtaining or identifying data from/about the individual (Deloitte, 2015). In other words, MP allows a company to tailor a product or service even more exactly in accord with the end users' wants and needs (Roumeliotis, 2015). Nevertheless, many failing examples of MC and MP have been observed, both at multinationals like Adidas (MiAdidas) and at small start-ups. Despite being announced as the answer for the increasing diversification of customer needs starting in the early 2000's, neither MC nor MP lived up to the expectations. Studies on a sample population have uncovered a failure rate of 20 percent within 15 months (Walcher and Piller 2013) for MC startups. This failure can be attributed to various factors such as lack of matching user expectations/needs (Ogawa and Piller 2006), high costs (Kaplan and Haenlein 2006), high complexity (Fox 2001) and lack of user engagement with customized products and the customization process itself (Bendapudi and Leone 2003). Due to technological progress in recent years in the field of digital manufacturing and AI, the first three factors are likely solvable. However, in recent times, clients seem to care increasingly more about the user experience, which makes the way customers go through the process of co-creation decisive. This research paper aims to expose and categorize contributing factors in the co-creation experience in order to get a better understanding of their influence on the process. The goal of this research is to point out possible leads to where possible UX related problems may lie, to increase customer satisfaction and hence to improve product configurators in sales conversion. The proposed research question that will be studied in this paper goes as follows: 'Can usability tests on web based MC co-creation tools lead to yet undiscovered UX related problems?' In order to get a better view of the problems, an extensive literature review and analysis of past and present MC trials has been done. To have a deeper understanding of the user experience a user study was devised.

2. Literature review and observation of product configurators

A literature study was conducted to assess already described and defined problem factors. The scope of this literature review was set on problems and problem factors concerning Mass-Customization co-creation for personalization through a digital user interface. Results were mapped on a scheme (appx. 1), which was later used to categorize existing tools, as a reference and as a tool to draft and later refine the used research methods. The scheme is built upon the principal agent relationship between customer and business (Franke and Piller, 2004).

Different MC approaches were observed (appx. 5), e.g.: in-store customization. However, this paper is focused on the online approach through product configurators (tools) only. Eighty-nine tools were catalogued with their attributes, these were chosen to provide a concise summary for each tool. These attributes are 'name', 'product category', 'interaction category', 'level of customizability', 'provision of

product visualization’, ‘provision of a professionally designed product as inspiration’ and ‘customization or personalization’.

Using an online configurator should be a simple and fun experience; advanced visualization of the tools contribute to this (Gandhi, Magar and Roberts, 2014). Certain configurators have become more time-consuming than others. This has led to a necessity to provide a pleasurable and more worthwhile user experience. Likewise, process interruptions caused by pop-ups and early user registrations disrupt the configurator flow. Another cause of user-discontent is the lack of personal treatment the configurator provides for the user. (Boynton and Pine, 1993). Tools that provide a helpdesk or a help function that enables the user to get assistance from a real life person, proved to achieve a higher conversion rate (Mueller, 2015).

Several online configurators allow users to either fully independently customize the product or choose from a set amount of inspirational starting points on which they can further customize. Research shows that customers prefer the latter; they would rather be inspired than to fully imagine their own product. (McDonald, 2019). Most configurators rely on a user’s active input, with various degrees of freedom and complexity. Others use data derived from other platforms (e.g. Spotify) that already contain information about the user’s preferences on the subject. This way, less active user participation is needed in the customization process.

3. Usability tests

3.1 Setup

In total six web-based MC co-creation tools were selected (**appx. 3 & table 1**) based on three conditions (appx. 2). These conditions were set to ensure each tool has proper merit to be analysed. To optimize the search for new problems, the selected tools needed to have solved most basic and common problems found during the literature review. Secondly, only web based tools were selected. Thirdly, the selected tools needed to encapsulate a broad variety of categories, interaction styles and input methods. Each tool was tested with a sample size of five. Each participant was asked to perform only one of the MC co-creation tools. In total 30 participants were tested for the six selected tools, with each participant testing only one tool.

Table 1: Features per tool					
Care of	New balance	Pied de poule	Ikea	AIAIAI	Kinematic dress
	color palette	color palette	color palette		
Long (duration)	medium (duration)	short (duration)	medium (duration)	short/medium (duration)	long (duration)

monotonous	dynamic	dynamic	dynamic	dynamic	dynamic
	pattern drag + selection + scale	pattern drag			
	independant part customizer		independant part composer	independant part composer	
	add text				
	visualisation	visualisation	visualisation	visualisation	visualisation
				expert suggestions	
indirect	direct	direct	direct	direct	direct

3.4 Test

All tests followed the same procedures (appx. 4). After an introduction, moderators asked participants to use the MC co-creation tool to customize the product or let the product be personalized. During the tests, participants were asked to think out loud and speak their thoughts openly to the moderator. Moderators did not watch the user's actions as this may influence a test-user's experience. However tests were recorded with a screen recorder. After completion, moderator and user revisited the tool, in order to ask specific tool-related open questions. Afterwards, a set of general open questions were answered by the user. Both general and tool-specific open questions were conducted, as those were most likely to provide the research with yet undiscovered faults. Lastly, all participants were asked to complete a closed question survey measured with a likert scale. The closed question survey created a way to indicate the weight of known faults in the current design of MC co-creation. It also gave the research leads towards some problems that might come with certain features. The results of the open questions were then used to further clarify the survey outcomes.

4.5 Results and discussion

Overall, the majority of participants is convinced of the added value of MC co-creation tools when purchasing required similar products. However, it was clear from the figures that both product configurators with a high degree and a low degree of complexity scored badly on a general level. A possible explanation may be that there must be sought for the golden mean. Moreover, a configurator tool with high complexity scored worse in customer satisfaction than a tool with low complexity.

The tools with low complexity offered a lower degree of customizability. Survey results have shown that this low degree of customizability does not match the users expectations, as observed in configurators featuring a pattern drag. The pattern drag function in itself is a satisfactory feature. Nonetheless, results show that the pattern

drag feature scores best in maintaining users interest when it is combined with more features. These include for example pattern selection, pattern scaling and independent part customizability. These results suggest users prefer having a high degree of control while using a pattern feature.

Product generators perform better in terms of ease of use when having less advanced controls. This may be due to users being unskilled or a user's unwillingness to learn how the tool operates. Whenever a user interface was perceived to have too advanced controls, users were inclined to request help from a more experienced person. A less complex user experience leads to higher satisfaction rates and eliminates users' need for external help. Thus, in order to satisfy frustrated users or address users' complaints about the level of difficulty of the tool, the simplification and streamlining of the tool and its UX is more important than providing real-life customer support.

In regards to ease of use, a high degree of control, or expert suggestions resulted in a positive increase hereof. However, tools with large amounts of complexity have a strong negative influence because of user incompetence, which results in a need to simplify interaction without taking away control.

The best results for a pleasant user interaction with a large amount of features, occurred when tools had a configurator flow with a mandatory order. A configurator with less features might give a pleasurable user interaction as well, but heightens the chance of user dissatisfaction with the degree of customizability.

The survey results showed that, in four of the tested tools, users feel an inability to express themselves properly. These tools share a similar low degree of control and their relatively low feature set (in this case: least amount of features scores the lowest). In order for a user to express himself properly, a high-level visualization of the outcome is required as well. Our test subjects proposed to add a 360° view of the product render, in favor of making the visualization more intuitive.

When using indirect questions to gather information about the user's preferences concerning the product, it is important that it is not similar to a survey. The use of a survey reduces the feeling of a personal approach during the customization process. The user expects the questioning to further develop and evolve depending on what they have stated in their previous answers. Creating a comfort zone by implementing familiar elements (e.g. favorite music, TV show, etc.) in the product configurator helps to put customers at ease and gain their trust.

When a tool requests intimate or sensitive information from the user by asking indirect questions, it is important that the user has confidence in the organization. The explicit request of personal data (such as name, e-mail, address, etc.) has a repellent effect as well. If users can log into another online platform, on which they already have an account (e.g. Google, Spotify, Facebook, etc.), they are more at ease.

A more advanced-looking user interface is generally disliked by users, as they might feel too unskilled or experience a lack of time to decently master the tool. Whenever a user interface was perceived as too advanced or complex, users prefer the help of a more experienced person. A less complex user experience leads to higher satisfaction rates with the tool, and eliminates users' need for external help. Thus, in order to satisfy frustrated users or address users' complaints about the level of difficulty of the tool, the simplification and streamlining of the tool and its UX is more important than providing real-life customer support.

6. Conclusion

The usability tests led to trajectories towards yet undiscovered problems. In like manner, the results led to a better understanding of the relation between the different facets of user experience in web-based Mass-Customization co-creation configurators.

In case of a low degree of customization the users did not like the final result because they could not express themselves and got bored quickly. In case of a high degree of customization the tools often got too advanced and complex. Users often got lost in the complexity and could not express themselves because using the tool was too challenging. The challenge lies in the balancing act between the certain features (e.g.: simplicity and level of customization) not over committing to others (e.g.: level of self-expression).

7. Appendices

Appendix 1.

Appendix 2.

Name	Product category	Interaction category	Input method	Level of customization	Render	Source of inspiration provided	Personalisation or customization
Care of	Vitamins	Click select	Indirect	High	N	N	Personalisation
Ikea	Closets	Click select	Direct	Low	Y	N	Customization
Pied de poule fermier scarf	Knitwear (scarf)	Pattern slide	Direct		Y	N	Customization
AIAIAI	Headphones	Click select	Direct	Medium	Y	N	Customization
New Balance	Footwear, digital knitwear	Pattern slide	Direct	High	Y	N	Customization
Kinematic dress	Dress			Very high			

Appendix 3.

Selection criteria
1. Solved most known problems tools
2. Tools needed to be web based
3. Varying categories, interaction styles and input methods

Appendix 4.

A. Set up

1. Set up eye tracking software
2. Set up camera
3. Check necessary open and closed survey question prints

B. Greeting

1. Thank the participant for coming.
2. Explain the research topic according to script.
3. Explain what they are about to do.
4. Let them choose the customization tool.

C. Participant undergoes phase 1: Purchasing a MC co-created product

1. Ask them to customize a product to their liking and purchase it
2. watch the participant closely for reactions and comments.
3. Abort when paying purchase

D. Participant and researcher review the tool

1. Ask tool specific questions
2. Ask general open questions
3. Provide participants with a sheet with closed Likert questions.

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